

On the Quality of Internet Users' Behavioral Patterns in Using Different Sites and its Impact on Taboos of Marriage: A Survey among Undergraduate Students in Mashhad City in Iran

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Abstract—Regarding the multi-media property of internet and the facilities that can be provided for the users, the purpose of this paper is to investigate the users' behavioral patterns and the impact of internet on taboos of marriage. For this purpose a survey technique on the sample size amounted 403 students of governmental guidance schools of city of Mashhad in country of Iran were considered. The results showed, the process of using various internet environments depends on the degree of the users' familiarity with these sites. In order to clarify the effects of the Internet on the taboos of marriage, the non – internet parameters also considered to be controlled. The t-test held among the internet users and non-users, indicated that internet users possess lower taboos of marriage. Extraction of the effects of internet via considering the effects of non-internet parameters, indicate that addiction to the internet, creating a cordial atmosphere, emotional communication, and message attractive factors have significant effects on the family's traditional values.

Keywords—Internet, taboos of marriage, family, mass communication, computer mediate communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE use of the Internet has increased dramatically over the past decade. In 2000, it was estimated that 400 million people had access to the Internet [1] In 2002, that number grew to more than 600 million individuals with Internet access[2], and in 2007 this number has reached to over 1,173,109,925 [3]. In Iran, many families now have one computer in the home and most of these families are also connected to the Internet. Statistic of internet users in Middle East on June 30, 2007, have been 19,539,300 that share of Iran have been 7,600,000 on June 30, 2007, statistics internet users in December 2000 have been 250,000 [3] concerning to this statistic rate grow internet users indicate in Iran. Main use for the Internet within the home is interpersonal

communication with friends and family primarily through the use of e-mail and instant messaging programs [4]. And With the creation and expansion of the Internet, computer-mediated communication (CMC) and word wide web (www) has become increasingly popular. Walther[5] defines CMC as synchronous [simultaneous] or asynchronous [delayed] Electronic mail and computer conferencing, by which senders encode in-text messages that are relayed from senders' computers to receivers and by world wide web(www) be head to searching about your needs for example; environment sexy, cart postal, science, information social politic economic and jock, game, soft ware..... CMC is used by individuals, groups, and organizations for many different functions, and an extensive social world has formed in what is often referred to as "cyberspace". Networks are made possible by cyberspace's capacity to support e-mail messaging, direct messaging, chat rooms, and similar types of online group interaction. It is chat room interaction and the formation of romantic relationships in chat rooms with which this study is primarily concerned [6].

Millions of such users individuals who use the Internet to meet strangers, flirt, and many times engage in highly sexualized conversations. In fact, Internet chat rooms have introduced unprecedented dynamics into marital relationships: never before has it been so easy to enjoy both the stability of marriage and the thrills of the dating scene at the same time. This phenomenon has become commonplace [7]; at any time of the day or night, individuals can be found in all types of chat rooms, ranging from apparently "innocent" ones Upon clicking a button on the screen with their cursor, users can post a message to be displayed to all other users logged into that particular chat room. Users have the option of sending private messages to particular individuals in the chat room. Upon reading another user's message, chat room users can post their own responses. If individuals possess a camera, they can see and/or be seen by their virtual partners; in many chat rooms, the viewing is live, in real time, while the conversation is taking place. In addition or be entrance of environment that emotion need to its (sexy, politic science, film, soft ware...)

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The present work defines it as such based on three factors. First, in Iranian culture (the background of this study), marriage is grounded within a powerful moral/cultural code where sexual – as well as emotional – exclusivity is steadily expected, if not required. This expectation or requirement is powerfully endorsed by public opinion; Thus, flirting and/or becoming sexual with potentially compatible strangers usually considered unacceptable within the boundaries of the moral, ethical, cultural, political, and religious codes governing the institution of marriage. These questions were analyzed within a quantitative methodology framework because research on the specific topic of online infidelity in use of internet different environment is still scarce.

In this paper we study the changing procedure of the users' behavioral patterns during internet use. In addition, we are to investigate the impact of internet on taboos of marriage. That is, whether the users' use of different environments of internet increases, decreases or remains fixed during the time. In addition, whether there is any difference between taboos of marriage of internet users and non-users and if so, which sites affect taboos of marriage?

Considering the multi-media property of internet and different ways of utilizing internet by its users, in this paper we study the changing procedure of the users' behavioral patterns during internet use. In addition, we are to investigate the impact of internet on the family traditional values. That is, whether the users' use of different environments of internet increases, decreases or remains fixed during the time. In addition, whether there is any difference between taboos of marriage of internet users and non-users and if so, which sites affect taboos of marriage?

Pursuing the significance of this research, students can be mentioned whose personalities are being shaped at this time, and what is more, as students they have an important role for the future of the society.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Specifics of computer-mediated communication (CMC)

The biggest impact of computer technology in society would be in communicating with one another [8]. Today's current events concerning the uses of computer-mediated communication (CMC) by individuals, including e-mail, blogs, chat rooms, computer-mediated communication (CMC) are electronic venues on the Internet where people can communicate with other Internet users. The typewritten word serves as the primary form of communication among people in chat rooms. Chat room users are provided with a field at the bottom of their computer screen in which they can enter any message that they wish. Upon clicking a button on the screen with their cursor, users can post a message to be displayed to all other users logged into that particular chat room. In addition, users have the option of sending private messages to particular individuals in the chat room. Upon reading another user's message, chat room users can post their own responses. Many people enjoy using chat rooms because they allow for anonymity. Concerning improvements in computer technology, chat room interactions are nearly synchronous, although the amount of asynchronization varies due to such

factors as modem speed, number of users logged on, and variation among CMC systems [5]. Love can form among internet users and this relationship effect on taboos of marriage, though terminology varies, many theorists point to high levels of emotional and behavioral involvement as a central feature of intimate or romantic relationships. Hatfield [9] conceptualizes passionate love in terms of strong and uncontrolled emotional engagement, while companionate love involves deep affection and feelings of interdependence. [10],[11] regards involvement, conceptualized as a partner's sense of caring or interdependence, as the central dimension of change in close relationships. Drawing from exchange theory, Levinger links increases in involvement to the exchange of mutually positive outcomes. Similarly, Berscheid and Reis [12], in their review of literature on the development of close relationships, conclude that relationships proceed systematically from more superficial to deeper and more interdependent levels of interpersonal involvement.

Anonymity is one of specific CMC to understand the effects of anonymity in interpersonal interactions we must look at how anonymity can influence communications at both the individual level and the group level. It has been suggested that people using the Internet are less concerned about social sanctions than are people in face-to-face interactions [13]. Conversely, the anonymity afforded by chat room environments may also encourage individuals to behave counter to the way they typically act. A shy person may behave in a more outgoing manner in a chat room than in a face to face interaction. Therefore, people who see themselves as introverted may appear extraverted to others in a chat room. Due to the anonymity in chat rooms, this trend for extraversion may become reversed, with people in chat rooms appearing more extraverted than they typically view themselves[14]. People treat others differently based on gender, race, age, ethnicity, physical disability, and attractiveness and social power hierarchies can also be based on these physical cues[15]. It is assumed that CMC acts as a filter that reduces the number of social cues that are available to individuals thus, CMC should create a more equal playing field for communicators [16],[17],[18]. Additionally, the anonymity of CMC frees members of lower status from their traditional social roles to behave in ways traditionally not associated with their group membership[19]. Therefore, researchers have hypothesized that in the absence of these cues, individuals who traditionally possess less power in society (e.g. women, minority group members, individuals with disabilities) should have increased power in an Internet environment [20],[21]. Spears and Lea [22] had initially theorized that once people understood how anonymity affects interpersonal communication in the Internet, they would begin to utilize this knowledge and use anonymity strategically to meet their own goals and needs of the communication. A highly regarded philosopher of our time, Jürgen Habermas, explicitly describes how people could build such a consensus. Several researchers have connected Habermas' theory to what we call the blogosphere, the network of bloggers[23].

Investigated whether CMC offer a platform for what he calls the 'ideal speech situation'. Conditions for the ideal speech situation are that everyone has equal access to the

communication, that there are no power differences between the participants and that the participants act truthfully towards each other. Since there is free software available, everyone with a connection to the internet has the ability to publish a weblog. CMC should be a place in which everyone can speak for him or herself without the boundaries that are set by traditional media; means that communication through CMC comes with certain changes in comparison to face-to-face communication. In some ways communication will be poorer and in others the communication will be enriched. Through a textual conversation people will have a different experience than when the same people have a conversation in a bar. On the other hand, using the internet it is possible to communicate cheaply and simply with people at the other side of the world.

Jürgen Habermas believes that there exist fundamental needs owned by all people quite freely, and will necessarily be discovered by anyone who sincerely enters a practical discussion[24]. Cordial atmosphere and emotional expressions are being shaped. In addition, the users talk about their needs and problems and consume their emotional energies in these environments, which can affect family traditional values.

In order to explain of effect of internet, be used of below theories:

Scarcity Hypothesis: This hypothesis is based on the Needs Hierarchy of Maslow. In its simplest form, Needs Hierarchy of Maslow implies public satisfaction. The non-satisfied material needs are prior to the social and aesthetical mental needs[25]. In this hierarchy, the lowest part contains psychological and biological needs. Next stage includes needs for safety, love and respect, self-assessment, self-actualization and recognition of understanding [25].

According to Inglehart, more value is considered for things presented less. If we want to associate this theory with internet, we can say that regarding the Needs Hierarchy of Maslow, there is little presentation of psychological needs. That is why in order to overcome these needs, internet users search them in different sites.

George Homenz: Here is the summary of Homenz's theories:
stimulus→action→ reward→value→action repetition (more use) →more effect[26].

Regarding Homenz's theory, stimulus is internet and its related environments with which action is done and by doing this action, the possibility for getting this reward is a lot; for this environment causes more satisfaction that leads to its value and the more use of it. Perhaps at the beginning the degree of satisfaction goes up, but little by little, its significance is reduced.

Rital Atkinson: He believes the more value is considered for the sender of the message, he more possibility for getting convinced by this message. He also believes that the receiver's evaluation by the sender is under the influence of two factors:

1. Credit,
2. Sender's attraction in receiver's view

By sender's credit, we mean the degree of his acceptability, depending on how professional he is in the subject and that whether he sounds reliable and spiteless or not. It seems if it becomes clear that the sender is trying to persuade us, his credit would possibly be diminished, because maybe we doubt

about his deceiving and spiteful message. Credit causes a change in our view, due to this fact that people accept the reasoning of a creditable source more seriously than that of a non-creditable one[27].

Message attractiveness: The second main factor in the sender's evaluation is the degree of the sender's attractiveness, which means how much the receiver is interested in the sender. Attractiveness is achieved through the mechanism of similarization[27]

People often like to be similar to those in whom they are interested, which itself leads to the imitation of the views of the concerned ones.

Danis Mcquail: Danis Mcquail has utilized Gratification type theories. The main assumption of the Use and Gratification pattern is that the addressee, more or less, looks for a content that provides the utmost gratification. The degree of gratification depends on people's needs and interests. The more they feel that the real content satisfies their needs, the more likely they choose that content. Blames and Katz are the rhetoricians of this pattern [28] Here is a model of Use and Gratification Pattern:

People's needs and interests→ content selection→ needs' estimation.

Windahl: In terms of mass media, that each of them does its own duty according to the specific expectations is tied to the receiver's reward. Windahl's model is that the more able is the content of the mass media to give rewards to the addressees, the more the amount of the use of that content will be.

Floor and Ball Rockeah: In their pattern, which is about the attachment to mass media, they believe that the important condition for the manifestation of effects is the amount of the attachment to mass media. A source, for which people feel more attached in order to gain information, is more powerful in causing effects in compared with a source that is not different from others and provides the information that lacks significance [28]. With the help of this theory, attachment to internet can be posed. Being attached to internet, the user will have less time to spend with his family, this makes family unimportant to him, and the result is the reduction of family values.

III. VARIABLES

Considering the exploratory studies and the attained ideas mentioned in the previous sections, in order to explain the impact of internet on taboos of marriage theoretically, we summarize our variables as follows to perform the relatedness between them through an experimental test.

A. Independent Variables

Independent variables include:

Internet mutual environments (chat, email...) which can have a direct influence on taboos of marriage as well as creating a cordial atmosphere and emotional relations, The amount of using internet, the time of using internet, different types of internet use, the duration of access to internet, Gender, Message attractiveness in general, as well as Iranian

and foreign ones, Using webcam and voice. (Operational independent variables are available at Table I)

B. Control Variables

Evaluating the pure effect of internet entailed some variables, apart from those related to internet, which are likely to have influence on family traditional values. Such variables are: using other types of mass media (the amount and kind of use of satellite, VCD, television, newspaper, magazine), how to spend leisure time, overseas travels, the amount of family's salary, parents' jobs and the number of children in one's family. In other words, the pure effect of internet was evaluated by keeping these variables fixed. To do so, first these variables are being associated with the dependent variable and if a significant relatedness is found, they will be controlled in order to evaluate the pure effect of internet.

C. Dependent Variable

In this study, the dependent variable is taboos of marriage. The independent and controlled variables are being associated with this variable (operational dependent variables are available at Table II)

IV. METHOD

This is a survey including a questionnaire as the devices. The studied population is high-school students of the third region in Mashhad, Iran. The sample volume is gained through the sample volume among the high school students of the third region in Mashhad was calculated as 300. Since the ratio of the number of female students to the whole population of students is (0.4353), and that of the male students is (0.5648), the girls' share in the sample volume is 130 and that of boys equals 170. Moreover, it was necessary that the number of internet users be enough for comparing and testing our hypothesis. Therefore, the sample volume was increased in order to be able to do these tests. The whole sample volume reached 403 people among which 180 were internet users. In this survey, the two-phase Accidental Cluster Sampling has been used.

Regarding the propounded hypothesis, first the variables were defined operationally, and then some variables were made, changed into questionnaires, and given to the respondents. In order to identify whether the variables used had a high range of accuracy or to what extent under the same circumstances, the same results will be gained, Cronbach's alpha was used. Then in order to make sure about the truth of

production of one factor in an indicator's production, Factorial Analysis was used.

Variables' Operational Definitions

A. Operational Definition of Independent Variables

Different Types of Internet Use

1.Email 2.Chat 3.Web log 4.Game 5.Scientific Information 6.Films 7.Jokes 8.Sexual Images 9.Music 10.News Sites; this variables had answered into rate of use to minute on week (Table I) Concerning to Table I, the rate of use of internet among all internet users in different types of use of internet environments per week.

TABLE I
 RATE OF USE OF INTERNET ENVIRONMENTS

Kinds of use internet	total	female	male
E-mail	63/5	74/16	54/17
Chat	172/15	251/91	133/85
Web log	42/85	35/059	49/16
Game	65/22	62/79	67/43
Science	67/30	75/41	60/20
Political	22/75	20/11	38/17
Social- economical	11/59	8/98	13/89
News	38/47	32/26	34/90
Sport	34/33	25/47	42/08
Cultural	22/08	24/76	19/37
View film	31/44	31/90	31/04
Jock	41	47/14	35/62
Sexual picture	32/75	16/05	49/94
Music	90/80	137/85	49/63
Soft ware	29	18/10	39/42
Cart postal	24/62	30/71	19/29

Table II shows independent variables of internet accompanied with variables and indicator's average (Each independent variables by codes: never= 0, Little= 1, moderate =2 , much= 3; very much= 4). Operational definition of dependent variable (taboos of marriages): Table II is the independent variable accompanied with variables and the indicators' averages. The obtained grades are fluctuated from zero to four, which means the closer the grade is to zero, lowest intensity; and the closer the grade is to four, the highest of intensity.

TABLE II
 OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF OTHERS INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Index	variables	Girl	Boy
Addiction to internet	Spending leisure time on internet	1.88	1.75
	Spending most of the time on internet	2.29	2.07
	Ignoring sleeping because of internet use	1.1	1.01
	Getting upset due to not having upset to internet	2.09	1.7
Creating a cordial atmosphere	removing loneliness	1.91	1.74
	Relations with internet friends	1.72	1.67
	Relations with opposite sex	1.62	1.98
	Searching a friend of opposite sex	1.69	2.10
	Friendship with opposite sex	1.41	1.84
Creating emotional relate	Opening one's heart	0.86	1.37
	Expressing interest	0.83	1.42
	Meeting internet friends	0.95	1.19
	Not being interested in quitting internet friends	2	2.17
Satisfaction of remaining unknown	Hiding one's gender	1.16	1.22
	Satisfied of their appearance not being influential in internet	1.94	1.69
	Introducing themselves as other people	1.55	1.38
Facilities to use	Voice & webcam	2.17	1.88
Message attractiveness	Singers' photos	2.39	2.16
	Actors and actresses' photos	2.29	2.03
	Listening to music	2.79	2.47
	Clothe fashion	2.04	1.39
	Make-up fashion	1.71	0.88
Attractiveness of Iranian and foreign messages	Iranian singers	1.98	1.89
	Foreign singers	2.21	2.12
	Iranian actors and actresses	1.96	1.76
	Foreign actor and actresses	1.9	1.65
	Iranian music	2.61	2.27
	Foreign music	2.21	1.88
	Iranian clothe fashion	1.39	0.9
	Iranian make-up fashion	1.17	0.72
	Foreign make-up fashion	1.41	0.8

Average of variable of addiction to internet for girls is 2.1 and for boys is 1.75 that indicate girls have more addiction to internet of boys, Average of variable of Creating a cordial atmosphere for girls is 1.5 and for boys is 1.9 that indicate boys have more average of girls, for variables creating emotional rate boys have more average of girls.

B. Operational Definition of Dependent Variable Result of Descriptive

According to Table III, the average of zero to four - **complete disagree= 0, disagree=1, moderate=2, agree =3; complet agree=4-** (zero, indicating lower Taboos of marriage and four indicating too Taboos of marriage) is the Taboos of marriage which are 2.2 among female users, 2.1 among male users and 2.2 among male non-users. As you can see, the Taboos of marriage of the female users and the male non-users are equal. In addition, among different groups of respondents the female non-users have higher Taboos of marriage. The existing discrepancy of Taboos of marriage between users and non-users is more than that of the male users and non- users, which indicates that the impact of internet on the Taboos of marriage of girls is more than its impact on the boys’.

V. RESULT

A. Descriptive Findings

1. Respondents’ Frequency Distribution

The respondents frequency is 403 among which 180 people are internet users, which means 66.44 percent of the respondents are internet users. Also 46.7 percent of these internet users are girls and the other 53.3 percent include boys. Considering all the respondents, 52.9 percent are female students and 47.1 percent are boys. Regarding their gender, among the whole sample volume, 39.43 percent are female users and 50.52 percent are the male ones.

2. The Amount of Internet Use

The average of the amount of internet use is 498.28 minutes a week, including 514.125 minutes a week for female users and 485.60 minutes a week for the male ones. This indicates a higher range of internet use among girls.

B. Quality of Internet Users’ Behavioral Patterns in Using Different Sites

1. The Quality of Use by Internet Users Compared with the Length of Internet Use

(What has been interpreted about the distribution graph depends upon the form of the graphs and is descriptive). Fig. 1 is the distribution graph of the length of internet use as compared with the amount of use of email, chat, games, educational environments and jokes (from the bottom to the top of the graph). Fig. 2 shows the length of internet use as compared with the amount of use of web log, news environments, films, jokes, sexual images, and music. According to Fig. 1 almost until the first ten months of getting familiar with internet, the use of different sites increases and after these ten months, the quality of the use of different sites will change. The use of chat increases among the users at the beginning and it goes on almost up to 40 months. Then it

stops and decreases very fast. Email use increases a little at the beginning, but after 20 to 40 months it decreases, and again after 40 months it increases. (Perhaps email replaces chatting). Use of game environments increases during the first 50 months and we see its reduction after that. The amount of use of educational- scientific sites is fixed at first, but it increases after 20 months of having access to internet. The use of joke sites reduces during the first 15 months, and then it increases in the next 50 months and again decreases after that. According to Fig. 2 at the beginning, the amount of use of web log decreases during the first 40 months, but after this time, web log use increases among students. Having access to news sites is almost not related to the degree of familiarity with internet. Watching films via internet reduces during the first 10 months, but then finds an intangible increase, but again decreases after 40 months. The amount of use of sexual images via internet has a little increase in almost 25 months, but then decreases. Listening to music via internet increases very fast and this increase goes on in 50 months of access, but decreases afterwards.

Fig. 1 Distribution the length of internet use with the amount of use of email, chat, games, educational environments and jokes

Fig. 2 Length of internet use with the amount of use of web log, news environments, films, jokes, sexual images, and music

2. The Quality of Use by Internet Users Compared with the Amount of Internet Use

(The comments on the Distribution Graph are according to the forms of Graphs and are descriptive.)

Figs. 3 & 4 indicate the average of the amount of different uses of internet environments as compared with the average of the amount of internet use. At first, the user gets familiar with a variety of internet sites. Then, this is the attractiveness of the internet environments, which leads to an increase in use; nevertheless, the Distribution Graphs can be described as follow: there is a correspondence between the amounts of internet use with the amount of chatting, so the students, who use internet a lot, enter chat rooms. Moreover, there is a direct relationship between the amount of using email and internet use, but if using internet reaches 1000 minutes a week, then using working with email decreases. Before the internet use reaches 400 minutes web log use is zero and after 400 minutes, the use of web log increases. When the internet use reaches 1440 minutes a week, web log use will be fixed. Playing games via internet, which increases when internet has been used for 1000 minutes, remains fixed after this time? Using news sites also increases until internet use reaches 1000 minutes a week and after this time, it becomes fixed. If we use internet up to 1200 minutes, using joke sites increases and it has a reduction after this time. In addition, there is the increase of education sites while the internet use is about 1000 minutes a week and after this time, it reduces. Use of sexual images is increased along with the use of internet. Installing programs from internet also increases in a direct way. The amount of listening to music via internet is also in direct linear relation with the amount of internet use.

Fig. 3 (from the bottom to the top) indicates the distribution graph of the amount of using educational environments, watching films, watching sexual images, installing software, and listening to music as compared with the amount of internet use.

Fig. 3 Distribution graph of the amount of using educational environments, watching films, watching sexual images, installing software, and listening to music with the amount of internet use

Fig. 4 The amount of internet use as compared with the amount of using chat, e-mail, web log, games, news, and jokes via internet

Fig. 4 shows the distribution graph of the amount of internet use (from bottom to the top) as compared with the amount of using chat, email, web log, games, news, and jokes via internet.

C. Explanatory Results

1. Hypotheses Testing

Those hypotheses, which are related to Taboos of marriage and the internet variables, and have passed the test, are as follow:

a. T-test Statistic

By means of t-test, this hypothesis passed the test (without controlling the variables). There is a significant difference between the students who have access to internet and those who do not, and Taboos of marriage. Those students, who have access to internet, have lower Taboos of marriage.

b. Variance Analysis

The variables of overseas travels, different groups of respondents, how to spend leisure time, and having access to internet which passed the test were tested by means of the Two-way Variance Analysis, so that we could evaluate the mutual effects of these variables on having or not having access to internet, and if they would pass the test in terms of mutual effects as well, we can come to the conclusion that these variables have mutual effects on each other.

By controlling these variables among those who have access to internet and those who do not, the mutual effects of overseas travels, how to spend leisure time, different groups of respondents, and Taboos of marriage were considered with the help of the Two-way Variance Analysis. This means that having access to internet by controlling the variables mentioned alone, do not affect the Taboos of marriage.

Also Using the Variance Analysis, this hypothesis passed the test and became significant at the level of 0.05. Comparing these groups, the difference between using internet just at home and using it at both home and a café net got significant. Those who use internet both at home and a café net, have lower Taboos of marriage than those who use internet just in

café nets, for it shows a great amount of attachment to internet or a great amount of its use.

c. Testing the Hypotheses

There is a significant difference between the amount of various types of internet use among high school students and its impact on Taboos of marriage. Some variables became significant. Those variables, which passed the test in terms of different usages of internet, are as follow:

By Pearson test correlation between independent variables and taboos of marriage show this result: effect of rate of use of chat (intensity = -0.21, sig = .01) that illustrate the increase of rate of use of chat, decrease taboos of marriage, rate of use of sexual sites (intensity = -0.22, sig = .01), that illustrate the increase of rate of use of sexual sites, decrease taboos of marriage, involving in cordial atmosphere (intensity = -0.38, sig = .01) that illustrate the increase of involving in cordial atmosphere, decrease taboos of marriage, involving in the emotional relations (intensity = -0.38, sig = .01), that illustrate the increase of emotional relations in internet, decrease taboos of marriage, acceptable in the mutual environments of internet (intensity = -0.24, sig = .01), that illustrate the increase accept in the mutual environments of internet, decrease taboos of marriage, use the attractiveness of internet environments (intensity = -0.26, sig = .01) that illustrate the increase of use of attractiveness of internet environments, decrease taboos of marriage, attractiveness of foreign messages (intensity = -0.32, sig = .01), that illustrate the increase of use of attractiveness of foreign messages in internet, decrease taboos of marriage, students use facilities of internet (web cam and voice) (intensity = -0.27, sig = .01), that illustrate students use facilities of internet, decrease taboos of marriage, rate of addiction to internet (intensity = -0.32, sig = .01), that illustrate rate of addiction to internet, decrease taboos of marriage. In the next step, since we mean to identify the pure impact of internet on family values, non-internet or control variables were also associated with family traditional values, and those, which became significant, were controlled by means of Pierson Separating Correlation Coefficient; this way the pure impact of internet was evaluated. Therefore, the hypotheses, which passed the test by means of Pearson Distribution Correlation Coefficient, are as in Table IV.

Addiction to internet with the intensity of -0.18 at the significant level of 0.05; creating cordial atmosphere with the intensity of -0.20 at the significant level of 0.05; the amount of emotional relations with the intensity of -0.22 at the significant level of 0.05; and the attractiveness of foreign messages at the significant level of 0.05 passed the test. (Table IV). Regarding the significance of these hypotheses, Habermas Theory of Relations (emotional relations and cordial atmosphere), Rital Atkinson's Theory (attractiveness of foreign messages), and DFlour and Bal Rokich's Theory (addiction to internet), were successful in the hypotheses testing.

D. Multi-variable Regression

For the simultaneous effect of the dependent and independent variables, Multi-variable Regression was used using a step-by-step method.

In the Regression Model, five variables have been inserted between the variable of taboos of marriage and all independent variables (control variables and internet variables) which are listed below based on the degree of importance:

1. The amount of use of satellite with the influence coefficient of -0.427.
2. Attractiveness of foreign messages with the influence coefficient of -0.23.
3. Attractiveness of Iranian messages with the influence coefficient of +0.392.
4. Creating emotional relation with the influence coefficient of -0.42
5. The amount of non-academic studies with the influence coefficient of +0.29.

These five variables have entered the model and explained 52 percent of the changes of taboos of marriage in all. This indicates that controlling all independent variables, the internet variables share 25 percent in the changes of taboos of marriage. In the Regression Model, three variables have been inserted between the variable of taboos of marriage and internet variables. Considering the order of their importance, these variables are listed as below:

1. Attractiveness of foreign messages with the influence coefficient of -0.365.
2. Creating emotional relations with the influence coefficient of -0.238.
3. Attractiveness of Iranian messages with the influence coefficient of -0.301.

These three variables have been effective in changes of taboos of marriage with a percentage of 35.

E. Causal Analytical Model (Path Analysis) of the Variable of Taboos of Marriage all Independent Variables

In the causal Model of taboos of marriage and all independent variables (MODEL I), the variables having direct influence on taboos of marriage are as follow:

1. Attractiveness of foreign messages has become significant with the intensity of -0.36 at the level of 0.05. (One-star signal shows the variables significance at the level of 0.05 and the two-star one shows its significance at the level of 0.01).
2. Attractiveness of Iranian messages getting significant with the intensity of +0.27 and at the level of 0.01.
3. Creating emotional relations with the intensity of -0.42 and at the level of 0.01 has become significant.
4. The amount of watching satellite programs has become significant with the intensity of -0.42 at the level of 0.01.
5. The amount of non-academic studies has got significant with the intensity of +0.29 at the level 0.01. (Actually, the variables having direct influence have become this effective by controlling all variables and in fact have evaluated the pure impact of internet.)

In the model, those variables having indirect influence have been illustrated with their intensity and direction on the arrows. Moreover, the level of significance has been identified

using a star on the figure of the intensity. Due to the length of the content, any explanation for the next model (model II) will be avoided.

1. Path Analysis Model of all Independent Variables and Taboos of Marriage. (Model I)

Coefficient of explanation (model II) =%52 Model I causal Analysis Model of all independent variables and taboos of marriage

2. Causal Analytical Model (Path Analysis) of the Variable of Taboos of Marriage Internet Variables

Coefficient of explanation (model II) =%35 Model II causal Model (Analytical) of taboos of marriage and internet variables

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates quality of internet user's behavioral patterns in using different sites and its impacts on taboos marriage in a survey method, for finding effect of internet on taboos of marriage have been of theories computer – mediate communication (CMC), communicative action theory, scarcity hypothesis, mass communication theories, dynamic group. According to the mentioned descriptive statistics, almost during the first ten months of getting familiar with internet, the use of its different environments increases, and after these ten months, there is a change in the way they use these sites. At the beginning chatting and playing games via internet, watching sexual images, listening to music and using joke sites increase to some extent; then there is a reduction in this usage. In fact, the user tends to remove the limitations with which s/he is confronted in the real world which itself reduces due to internet use. Email use increases at the beginning; however, web log and educational- scientific sites are not used a lot at first, but after some time of getting more familiar with internet, the use of these sites increases. Perhaps this change is due to this feeling of the internet user that using these sites would be useful to him/her or that s/he has not wasted his/her time. With the help of the Multi-variable Regression, having all variables inserted including internet and non-internet variables, the share of internet variables in explaining taboos of marriage was 25 percent. These variables were associated with the creation of emotional relations and the amount of referring to the attractiveness of foreign messages that had negative impact on taboos of marriage. Using Pearson Correlation Coefficient by controlling all non-internet variables, the pure impact of internet variables on taboos of marriage (variables that passed the test) were as follow: addiction to internet and crating cordial atmosphere, creating emotional relations, and the attractiveness of foreign messages. Result show CMC theories, Habermas Theory (emotional relations and cordial atmosphere), Rital Atkinson's Theory (attractiveness of foreign messages), and DFlour and Bal Rokich's Theory (addiction to internet), were successful in the hypotheses testing.

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TABLE III
 THE DEPENDENT VARIABLE ACCOMPANIED WITH BUOIES AND THE INDICATOR'S AVERAGES

The indicator	Buoies	Female users	Female non-users	Male users	Male non-users
Taboos of marriage	1. Friend marriage 2. Not having sex before marriage by girls 3. Not having sex before marriage by boys 4. Proposing to boys by girls 5. Marrying one who has had sex formerly 6. Making friends with one we are going to marry.	2.2	2.5	2.1	2.2

TABLE IV
 PARTIAL CORRELATION COEFFICIENT WITH CONTROLLING NON-INTERNET VARIABLE (BETWEEN INTERNET AND TABOOS OF MARRIAGE)

		Addiction to internet	Cordial atmosphere	Emotional relations	Attractiveness of foreign messages
Taboos of marriage	Intensity	-0.186	-0.202	-0.223	-0.207
	p-value	0.05	0.033	0.019	0.029